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DIALLS Analysed online interactions.

Analysing computer-mediated discussions on the DIALLS platform.

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For each age group (pre-primary, primary, secondary), each analysed online interaction is presented in the following way:

Wordless text - Concepts at stake in the lesson - Source of the coded discussion

Structural features

Coding table

Interpretation table

1. Pre-primary

1.1. Owl bat, Bat owl - Tolerance - HUJI (HUJI_A_EAir+EZiu_6)

10 contributions - 6 threads. Minimum length 1, maximum length 3.

All initiated by teachers.

1.1.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis		Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts: Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
1	hello 1st grade, we were excited to receive your works we're sending you ours right away	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Managerial (MA) - Inviting (IN) [invitation to send work]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we", "ours" but task-managing contribution]
2	we thought that the last picture of the book where all the flying animals helped each other is the most important picture in the story.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	Description (DS)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class
3	they connected together hand in hand near the moon and their moms talked	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Description (DS)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher [not specified]
4	we think that the last picture they cooperate and connect together, at the end they knew each other and became friends, they became friends and played together	- Tolerance - Implicit Use [reference to acceptance of others] - Inclusion - Implicit Use [reference to participation to a group]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class

4-1	we agree with you the most power we have is when we are together	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC) 	Teacher 1	Whole Class
5	waiting for your artefacts...	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
5-1	we sent them, what do you think?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Managerial (MA) - Inviting (IN) [demand of feedback] 	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we", but task-managing contribution]
5-2	we sent you a collage of our artefacts	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we", but task-managing contribution]
6	we see that you have put a lot of effort into your workds, the pictures are very pretty, and some of them are similar to ours...	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) [form of acceptance of artefacts] - Synthesis / Constrast (SY/CO) ["some of them are similar to ours"] 	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole class
6-1	thank you very much. We also think that your art works are similar to ours. And the idea of cooperation and friendship is repeating in the artefacts	Inclusion - Implicit Use ["cooperation and friendship"]	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) [form of acceptance of artefacts] - Synthesis / Constrast (SY/CO) 	Teacher 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Whole Class - Teacher Enunciator Whole class [second sentence]

1.1.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This interaction is composed of two thematic episodes: the first one is constituted of threads 1 to 4, and the second one of threads 5 and 6. The first thematic episode correspond mainly to cumulative dialogue, with an accumulation of statements (contributions 2, 3, 4) and little collaboration (only contribution 4-1 is co-constructive). The second thematic episode is mostly regulatory, as it is focused on the exchange of cultural artefacts between the classes. Thus, the whole online interaction is weakly dialogic, as one could have expected from an interaction at the pre-primary level focused on the production and exchange of cultural artefacts. We can assume that most of the teacher-guided dialogue between students was done orally.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The online interaction appears weakly dialogic (see above). Nevertheless, from a conceptual standpoint, contribution 4 is to be noted, as it contains a Concept-Oriented Interpretation relating both to Tolerance and Inclusion, which is a conceptually advanced contribution at the pre-primary level.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	During the online dialogue, work on the key notions of TEI is mainly done during the first thematic episode, where students implicitly use these three notions while reconstructing the narration of the text. However, we can hypothesise that this work is done orally during all the lesson (i.e. also during the time corresponding to the second thematic episode), as the last contribution (6-1) also presents an use of Inclusion despite being in a thematic episode more focused on the cultural artefacts.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	<p>The role of the teachers during this interaction is complex, as they take alternatively different roles. Teachers are task-managers in thread 1 and 5, which are respectively focused on facilitating the online interaction between the teachers and managing the work on artefacts. They are also mediators in threads 2, 3, 4, using mainly the voice of the whole class (except in thread 3). The role of teachers are mixed in thread 6, as they are both task-managers (facilitating the online interaction), mediators (using the voice of the class) and guides, as they synthesize the ideas underpinning the artefacts (e.g. "<i>the idea of cooperation and friendship is repeating in the artefacts</i>" in contribution 6-1). There is to be noted that the teachers tend to hide themselves, mostly use the voice of the whole class when mediating, and use their voice as enunciated by the whole class when doing task-management.</p>
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

1.2. Baboon on the Moon - Empathy / Belonging - NOVA_A_mam_cc+mc_8_ENG_1

8 contributions - 5 threads - Minimum thread length: 1 - Maximal thread length: 3

All threads were initiated by teachers

1.2.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Belonging				
1	Home is where we like to live (planet earth, where our brothers and sisters and parents are, a clean place, family, pets).	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
1-1	We agree with you because the Earth is also our home, but sometimes the Earth is dirty. We also think that home is the family. We also think that home is where we and our friends are, is where we are happy.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Justification (JU) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) ["<i>but sometimes the Earth is dirty</i>"] - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC) 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
1-1-1	Perfect, we all agree. In here, the family is the most important. Thank you "family from Oeiras County"	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Definition (DF) [" <i>family is the most important</i> " to the definition of home]	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
2		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]

3	Construction of our home.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague as it refers to an artefact, outside of the debate]</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague as it refers to an artefact, not the text]</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-1	We're looking forward for your artefacts.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class
4	Such special homes. We liked very, very much.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague as it refers to an artefact, outside of the debate]</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague as it refers to an artefact, not the text]</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) [acceptance of the artefacts]	Teacher 1	- Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified] - Whole Class ["we"]
5	For us, home is nature, rainbow, sun, joy, beach, summer, a warm place. It is also shining, amazing and gorgeous. It's the place where toys are pretty.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded [too vague as it refers to an artefact, not the text]</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["us"]

1.2.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This interaction is very short. The students mostly discuss with each other in the first and third thematic episode (thread 1 and 4-5), the second episode (thread 3) being mainly regulatory and focused on artefact production. Nevertheless, the first thematic episode is as dialogic as one can expect from students at the pre-primary level, the dialogue in this episode being both cumulative (statements, acceptances), collaborative (contribution 1-1 is co-constructive) and argumentative (contribution 1-1 contains a justification and a contrast). The brief discussion about the produced artefacts within the third thematic episode (threads 4 and 5) is again mostly cumulative. The core of students' work here is in the production of cultural artefacts, which is not visible in online data.

Form of the dialogue	What is the quality of their dialogue?	From the dialogicity point of view, the first thematic episode is as dialogic as one can expect from students at the pre-primary level, the dialogue in this episode being both cumulative (statements, acceptances) and argumentative (contribution 1-1 contains a justification and a contrast). On the conceptual level, students propose several times tentative definitions of "home", which is to be noted considering their pre-primary level.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key concepts of the text?	The interaction is not focused on the key concepts of Tolerance, Empathy and Inclusion: there is no contribution using these concepts. There is either no trace of a reconstruction of the narration of the text from students. In the first thematic episode, the conceptual work is mainly aimed at the notion of Belonging through the exploration of the definition of "home". In the second thematic episode, students build their cultural artefacts (thread 3) and briefly discuss them (threads 4 and 5), mainly focusing on the definition of home (e.g. contribution 5). This may be related to the DIALLS lesson plan for this sequence, since the production of cultural artefacts about "home" is time-consuming and do not allow teachers to simultaneously do a conceptual work on Empathy with their students. Contribution 5, which appears "out of context" regarding the previous contributions, suggests a lot of face-to-face discussions which are not visible in online data.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	In the first and third thematic episode of this interaction, the teachers are exclusively in the role of mediators, only using the voice of the whole class in their discourse (excepted a sentence in contribution 4 where the voice is not specified). In the beginning of the second thematic episode (thread 3) they seem to shift to the role of task manager to organise the production of cultural artefacts in both classes, taking again the discourse with their own voice. At least on online data, teachers do not appear to guide students, maybe to let them build their cultural artefacts as creatively as possible.
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

1.3. *Big finds a Trumpet* - Inclusion - UCAM (UCAM_AM_BH_A_7)

7 contributions - 3 threads :

1 - Length 1, initiated by teacher

2 - Length 4, initiated by teacher

3 - Length 2, initiated by teacher

1.3.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis		Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts: Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
1	At the beginning they were happy because they were playing ball together and they both had big smiles on their faces.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) ["together"]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First-Level Interpretation (FLI) ["they were happy"] • Description (DS) ["they were playing ball together"] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) ["they were happy"] • Justification (JU) ["because" gives reasons for accepting the given interpretation] 	Teacher 1	Teacher [no specific voice indicator] Enunciator Whole Class [language used]
2	In the middle when Big found the trumpet, small was very angry because he felt out and he didn't like the noise of the trumpet. He played all day and all night, perhaps Big needs more practice on the trumpet.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) ["felt out"] Empathy-Implicit Use (IU) ["very angry"]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description (DS) ["Big found a trumpet", "he played all day and all night"] • Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) ["felt out" refers to inclusion] • First-Level Interpretation (FLI) ["perhaps Big needs more practice"] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) ["small was very angry"] • Justification (JU) ["because" gives reasons for accepting the given interpretation] 	Teacher 1	Teacher [no specific voice indicator] Enunciator Whole Class [language used]
2-1	We think that Big needs to play the trumpet quietly so he does not annoy Small.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) [specific action to reach a compromise]	Self-Involvement (SI) [proposition of alternative action to solve the problem]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]

2-1-1	We think that is a good idea, but it might be tricky to play quietly so we think Big should choose a different time to play on the trumpet maybe when small is busy playing something else.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) [specific action to reach a compromise]	Self-Involvement (SI) [proposition of alternative action to solve the problem]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accepting/Discarding (AC/DC) ["we think that is a good idea"] • Synthesis/Constrast (SY/CO) ["but it might be tricky"] • Justification (JU) ["so"] • Co-Construction (CC) [formulation of a new idea basing on the previous contribution] 	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
2-1-1-1	But they are friends. They should play together. Maybe Big and Small should both playtrumpets at the same time.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) [specific action to increase collaboration]	Self-Involvement (SI) [proposition of alternative action to solve the problem]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesis/Constrast (SY/CO) ["But they are friends"] • Stating (ST) ["They should play together"] • Co-Construction (CC) [expandin 	Teacher 2	Teacher [no specific voice indicator] Enunciator Whole Class [langage used]
3	In the end, Big was very sad because the big person showed him how it feels when you blow loud noises at friends. Maybe Big feels bad that he didn't play with small because the trumpet distracted him. Now they are friends because they play together and are smiling and hugging.	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to non-participation, "together"] Empathy- Implicit Use (IU) ["very sad", "how it feels"]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description (DS) ["the big person showed him..."] • Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) ["they are friends because they play together" refers to inclusion] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) ["Big was very sad", "Now they are friends"] • Justification (JU) ["because" gives reasons for accepting the given interpretations] 	Teacher 1	Teacher [no specific voice indicator] Enunciator Whole Class [langage used]
3-1	What would you do if somebody didn't want to play your game?	Inclusion-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to non-participation]	<i>Not coded</i> [the contribution is not about the wordless text]	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher [no specific voice indicator] Enunciator Teacher [the question is part of the lesson]

1.3.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	The online discussion between students is mediated by teachers. The interaction is constituted of two thematic episodes, the first one from contribution 1 to 3 and the second being only contribution 3-1. Most of the dialogicity of the interaction is concentrated in thread 2, as the dialogue is initially mostly cumulative, with a more argumentative and co-constructive shift at contribution 2-1-1. Students answer to each other as much as one can expect from pre-primary students, and co-construct their self-involvement (contributions 2-1-1 and 2-1-1-1).
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	Despite an overall low conceptual quality (which was to be expected for pre-schoolers), the mediation by teachers permits a highly dialogic online interaction and co-construction (2-1-1 and 2-1-1-1), with a dialogue of a co-constructive type and diverse complex Dialogue Acts (as Justification or Synthesis/Contrast). Keeping in mind that this lesson concerns pre-primary students, this online dialogue could then be considered as highly dialogic.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The concept of "Inclusion", at the core of the wordless text, is used in all contributions, but never mentioned explicitly, let alone defined. However, students quickly achieve to attain self-involvement in the text (contribution 2-1), proposing alternative actions from Big to solve the problem depicted in the text. This self-involvement is the center of the thread corresponding to half of the online dialogue (thread 2).The text is then seen as a space where actions can be taken: even if "Inclusion" is not conceptualized and verbalized, students seem to attain here a "operational" understanding of inclusion, as it seem to be the main motivation in their propositions of alternative actions (see thread 2). One can also observe implicit mentions to Empathy in contributions 2 and 3, with an overlap between Empathy and Inclusion which could be formulated as "sad/angry if/when not included". This concrete link with feelings seems to help children make inclusion-oriented interpretations in the text.

Task - Narration and ethical concepts	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	The dialogue is much more focused on the specific wordless text than on the general concept at stake (<i>i.e.</i> Inclusion) itself.
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	Both teachers are here exclusively in the role of mediators, as we could have expected from a pre-primary lesson. The eventual task management was probably made orally, and there is no trace of a regulatory type of dialogue on the online data. Similarly, eventual guidance from the teacher was probably effected orally, and the online dialogue between teachers is focused on the co-construction of students' self-involvement in the wordless text, culminating with the last contribution (3-1).
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	The mediating role is so pregnant in this sequence that the teachers do not always precise explicitly that they speak for the class (using a "we"), as if their voices were embodying the voice of the class, with the enunciator "whole class" in contributions 1, 2, 2-1-1-1 and 3.

1.4. Owl Bat, Bat Owl - Tolerance // Big Finds a Trumpet - Inclusion - ID10_Lesson 6_UNIC_A

25 contributions - 10 threads. Minimal thread length 1, maximal thread length 6.

All threads initiated by teachers.

1.4.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis		Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts: Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
1		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
2		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-1	Because now they are happy and having fun together. They help each other. In the end they made a circle showing that they were loved. That is how they learned to respect each other and can now live together as loved ones.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) ["together"] - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others] - Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) ["respect each other"] 	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-1-1	Great answer. We agree with you!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]

4		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
4-1	The part of the story we chose as the most important was when the owl found the bat and the bat found the owl	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
5	which part of the story was most the important for the plot?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
5-1	We believe that the wind disturbed the families and caused panic and a big problem	<i>Not coded</i>	- Description (DS) - First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
5-1-1	Then they realized that it was important for them to stop arguing and for the moma to help each other finding their children.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
5-1-1-1	what do you think?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question]
5-1-1-1-1	Because now they are happy and having fun together. They help each other. In the end they made a circle showing that they were loved. That is how they learned to respect each other and can now live together as loved ones.	- Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) ["together"] - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others] - Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) ["respect each other"]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
5-1-1-2	The part of the story we chose as the most important was when the owl found the bat and the bat found the owl	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
6	Why was it important that the two families learned to live together and share?	Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) ["live together"]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question]

6-1	they were all happy. They had fun together. They all played together and shared their house. They had a floor each.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) ["played together"] - Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to acceptance of others] 	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
7		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
8	What are the leading characters of the story good at?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question]
8-1	The leading characters of the story are good at playing with the ball. Big has a little trouble with his hands and he's going to get the ball all the time. He did not know how to play the trumpet very well and made the others tired. However in the end, he returned to his friend and they played ball.	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to exclusion]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class [explicit mediation]
9	Why is Big an important leading character in the story?	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question]
9-1	Big is an important leading character because he is a very good friend. He plays with his friend fairly and after realizing his mistake, he apologized and showed his love with a hug	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to (non-)participation to a specific group]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) 	Teacher 1	Whole Class [explicit mediation]
9-1-1	Big is an important leading character because with his behavior he shows to us that we must be good with our friends, to help them if they need something that we can help, but also to accept them as they are.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others] - Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to accepting others] 	Self-Involvement (SI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
10	What part of the story moved you?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question]

10-1	We were moved by the end of the story, when the two friends hugged each other and continued playing ball happily.	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to participation to a group]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
10-1-1	We were moved by the fact that: 1. Big finds a way to do things without his hands. And 2. shows a lot of love to his friend. We were also moved by his friend who accepted him back	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to participation to a group]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]

1.4.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This online interaction does not appear as highly dialogic: students rather seem to react to teachers' questions than to discuss together, with disconnected statements produced to answer teacher's invitations. Students may have discussed together orally, but there is no indicator of this on the online data. As such, students' online contributions (mediated by the teacher, often with the voice of the class) are mostly corresponding to a cumulative dialogue. This could have been expected from a discussion at the pre-primary level.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The interaction rather lowly dialogic (see above). However, from a conceptual standpoint (see below), students seem to efficiently link the notions of TEI and the two wordless texts.

Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The dialogue is mostly centered on the two texts <i>Owl Bat, Bat Owl</i> and <i>Big finds a trumpet</i> , and most of the contributions focus on the narrative reconstruction of the texts. Nevertheless, students often use the concepts of Tolerance, Inclusion (both being the main aim of one of the texts) and Empathy in their interpretations. Most of the interpretations produced by students are then at least partly concept-oriented, and there is even one Self-Involvement (contribution 9-1-1), which is to be noted for pre-primary students. There is also to be noted that the concepts of Tolerance, Empathy and Inclusion are frequently used together in concept-oriented interpretations, which can be an indicator for the constitution of a global cultural literacy rather than an isolated work on each notion.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	In this lesson, teachers are mostly both mediators and guide, as they're alternatively asking specific guidance questions to foster students' reflexion on the texts and on TEI, and transcribing their answers on the DIALLS online platform. As such, the voice used by the teachers are constantly changing during the discussion, shifting between the whole class and the teachers themselves. Furthermore, when the voice of the teacher is used, it is alternatively enunciated as the teacher him/herself (during guidance) or as the whole class (during mediation).
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

2. Primary

2.1. *The Hedgehog and the City* - Social responsibility / Social/civic competence - HUJI (HUJI_B_EPrb+ETis_7)

18 contributions - 11 threads - Minimum thread length: 1 - Maximal thread length: 3

All threads were initiated by teachers

2.1.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Social responsibility / Social/civic competence				
1	good morning ET, fourth grade	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT) [greetings are not strictly speaking part of the task]	Teacher 1	- Teacher [no specific voice indicator] - Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]
2	good morning fourth grade students at EP school	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT) [greetings are not strictly speaking part of the task]	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]
2-1	good morning we are excited and happy to cooperate	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT) [greetings are not strictly speaking part of the task]	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
2-1-1	my video isn't working yet	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [use of the online platform]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["my"]
3	our suggestions to use the money: we would donate it to needy NGO's such as Pe'ula	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]

4	to poor people who have no money to purchase medicine we would give the money to sick people at hospital for medicine we would give to people who need more than we do such as NGOs	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
5	we would donate to hospitals	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
6	we would donate to people with cancer	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
7	I would open a restaurant for people with no money	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [suggestion of alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Student ["I" designates a student more than the teacher]
8	we would donate to animals and less space for construction donate food for animals	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [suggestion of alternative action]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
8-1	we decided to improve our community's life and eventually it was decided to invest in building a park where there is a meeting place for everyone a space for animals facilities swings benches drinking source garbage bins tables trees bushes flowers and grass a fountain a meeting place for parents with children recycle bins things that everyone loves	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Explicitly mentioned ["improve our community's life" refers to a social and civic competence]	Self-Involvement (SI) [suggestion of alternative action]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Justification (JU) ["Things that everyone loves" is a reason for accepting the features of the park] 	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
9	the ideas shared by both classes: thinking about building an animal park	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Synthesis/Contrast (SY/CO) ["the ideas shared by both classes"]	Teacher 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teacher [no specific voice indicator] - Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]
9-1	great the groups are designing the park plans once they're done I'll upload the artefacts	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [task-management "the group are designing the park plans", use of the online platform "upload"]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["I"]

10	the difference between the classes is that in my class they suggested what to do with the money for the community not only by building a park but also by giving to the needy and to NGOs	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Synthesis/Contrast (SY/CO) ["the difference between the classes"]	Teacher 2	- Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["my class"] - Whole class ["my class suggested..."]
10-1	in the initial discussion we did bring up a lot of other ideas when we came to the insight that community is a life of partnership mutual aid solidarity and cooperation it was decided to strengthen the connections between everyone who lives in the community and they agreed that building a park as an inviting meeting place for the whole community to strengthen between them closeness and connection	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others] Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [specific action to increase diversity]	Definition ["community is a life of partnership..." and the following refers to social and civic competence]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synthesis/Contrast (SY/CO) ["we did bring up a lot of ideas..."] • Justification (JU) ["when we came to the insight..." gives reasons to accept "it was decided to strengthen..."] • Co-Construction (CC) [the teacher extends his/her class' reasoning because of the challenge given by the other teacher] 	Teacher 1	- Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["my class"] - Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we did bring up"] - Whole class ["they agreed"]
11	T when do you think you will upload the artefacts?	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [task management]	Teacher 1	- Teacher [no specific voice indicator] - Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]
11-1	are you still here?	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [task management, use of the online platform]	Teacher 1	- Teacher [no specific voice indicator] - Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]
11-2	hi T I've uploaded the artefacts	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about concepts]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [task management, use of the online platform]	Teacher 2	- Teacher [no specific voice indicator] - Enunciator Teacher [no specific enunciator indicator]

2.1.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This online interaction between students is mediated by teachers. Students do not seem to effectively answer to each other, with a lot of very short threads within a cumulative episode (contributions-threads 3 to 8 in particular). Dialogicity seems to be more sustained during the following phase of the online dialogue (threads 8 to 10), with a shift to a more argumentative dialogue, but threads stay short (length 2 in this second phase) and there is few interaction between the students. The last thematic episode (thread 11) is regulatory, as teachers close the online dialogue. There is very few traces of collaborative dialogue in this exchange, whereas in the dialogue acts or in the use of polyphony.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The overall quality of the dialogue appear rather low, whereas from the conceptuality or dialogicity perspectives. Most of the contributions corresponding to low-dialogical moves (statements or managerial) and a long episode of cumulative dialogue (contributions-threads 3 to 8). Threads 8 to 10 show more dialogicity, with contributions using contrastive and justificative moves within a more argumentative dialogue.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key concepts of the text?	After a first introductory phase (contributions 1 to 2-1-1) to initiate the discussion, students jointly work on the text during a second phase (contributions 3 to 8-1). A third phase of the dialogue is composed of three very short discussions (threads 8 to 10) with a reflection on the ideas produced before and a deepening of concepts. However, during this third phase, the proper conceptual work is limited, as only two contributions focus explicitly on "Social and civic competences" (contributions 8-1 and 10-1) with only one defining it (10-1). This last contribution is nevertheless co-constructed, as it follows the challenge of one teacher, and detailed. A fourth and last phase of the dialogue (threads 11 and 12) is strictly dedicated to task management (productions and uploading of cultural artifacts) and as such the contributions of this phase do not show and use of concept nor focus on the text. The task here lie mostly in the cultural artifact and in the oral discussions, and it is difficult to analyse it without them.

Task - Narration and ethical concepts	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	The students immediately involve themselves in the narration of the text (contributions 3 to 8-1). A fourth and last phase of the dialogue (threads 11 and 12) is strictly dedicated to task management (productions and uploading of cultural artifacts) and as such the contributions of this phase do not show and use of concept nor focus on the text. The task here lie mostly in the cultural artifact and in the oral discussions, and it is difficult to analyse it without them.
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	Teachers take in this online discussion two main roles : task manager and mediator. There is few traces of teacher's guidance for students in the online discussion, but one can expect that the students directly involving themselves in the narration of the text in contribution 3 is due to oral teacher's guidance, inaccessible on online data. The task management role is more visible at the beginning and the end of the interaction, with interaction-facilitating off-task contributions (contributions 1, 2 and 2-1) or managerial contributions (contributions 2-1-1, 11, 11-1 and 11-2).
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	The teachers adopt a mediation role (contributions 3 to 8-1), in order to develop the interaction between classes. This mediation phase appears to be troubled in contribution 9-1 where one teacher takes again the role of task-manager. This seems to disrupt the mediation role in the thread 10, where teachers both speak with their own voice and the voice of the class, which does not correspond to standard meditating contributions where the teacher usually "steps aside". In particular, the teacher in contribution 10-1 use him/herself and the class both as a voice and as an enunciator, maybe because of the argumentative (and maybe emotional) tension created by the other teacher who compared classes in contribution 10 .

2.2. Baboon on the Moon - Empathy / Belonging - NOVA (NOVA_B_EJib_mc+EIsh_8)

28 contributions - 23 threads - Minimum thread length: 1 - Maximal thread length: 3

All threads were initiated by teachers

2.2.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Belonging (home)				
1	Group 2 (3 boys) thinks, unanimously, that home/house is: a space where we feel good; a safe space; a place where we can play, a home to live with our family; a home where we like to live,	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (group)
2	Group 3 (5 boys) says: a home for us is a place where we feel good. Because our family, our things and our memories are there. We also think home is a place to relax, because we get more relaxed with our family.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (group)
3	Group 4 (4 girls) has several opinions: a house for me is the place where I feel good; a house for me is the place where I sleep and eat; a house for me is the place where I live and have my family near me.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Student(s) ["for me" multiple times]
4	Group 5 (5 boys) says: For us, home is like a nest of humans with protection, food and a place for needs. It is also a place to rest. It has a kitchen, a living room and a large corridor.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (subgroup)

4-1	We liked the idea of "nest of humans", we wouldn't remember that. It's a very cute idea. Your ideas and ours are different, but they're all good ideas.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) [last sentence]	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]
4-2	It doesn't take a big house to feel better and happier.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [not a proper definition but a remark on the definition of "home". It is as such a definitory conceptual work]	<i>Not coded</i>	Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
5	Group 6 (4 girls) says: For us home is a place where we feel safe, where we feel comfortable. A house is a home where we like to stay.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (subgroup)
6	Group 1 (2 girls, 2 boys) says: A home is a place where we all live and feel good. It's a space where we survive and has: a room where we warm ourselves at night, a kitchen where we feed ourselves and a bathroom where we make our needs.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (subgroup)
6-1	Your answer was a good effort, we share the same ideas, they are very similar to ours.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) [last proposition]	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we", "ours"]
7	Group 5_G2 (2 boys, 2 girls): We think that our house has family. Because we love our family. Our house is a place where we feel happy.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Student(s) (subgroup)
7-1	Some of us agree with your idea, but there are those here who argue that there are people who live without their families and they still have a home.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [not a proper definition but a remark on the definition of "home". It is as such a definitory conceptual work]	<i>Not coded</i>	Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO)	Teacher 1	Student(s) (subgroup)
8	Group 3 (1 girl, 2 boys): To have a house is to have food to eat, to rest, and to keep warm.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Student(s) (subgroup)
8-1	We agree. Some of us thought so too.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) [last sentence]	Teacher 1	Whole Class

9	Group 2 (3 boys, 1 girl): To have a house is to have a family, to have brothers, mother, father, grandfather, uncle and friends. To have love, friendship, peace and relax with our united family.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Student(s) (subgroup)
10	Group 1_G1(2 boys, 1 girl): For us, home is our family. Because without it, it wouldn't be the same, we wouldn't be happy or loved. Because our family is more important than our house.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Student(s) (subgroup)
11	Group 4 (2 boys, 1 girl): For us, home is to have a family and a house, it is to have a lot of happiness. For us, home is where there is a mother and a father, to help. It is where we are happy.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Student(s) (subgroup)
12	We belong to this place because in this house we have memories that make us feel happy; we have a kitchen where we can have food; a room where we can rest, and a bathroom where we can make our needs.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
13	We belong to this place because: we need people to help us; we need a place to live; we need food; we need a place where we feel safe.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
14	We belong to this place because: our house is a home where we can relax and hide our secrets.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
15	We belong here because this is where our family, our favourite things, food and this is where we feel good.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
16	We belong to this place (school) because this is where our friends are, and this is where we feel good.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
17	We belong to this place (planet) because we have family, home, work, school and leisure (sports). Here we feel happiness, love and security.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class
18	We belong to this place because here we have feelings that affect us and so we can all live better and in harmony.	Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to acceptance of others]	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 3	Whole Class

19	Here we are deciding what to do.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [task-management]	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we" but managerial contribution]
20	Here we are divided into groups to make the cultural artefact.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [task-management]	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we" but managerial contribution]
21	These were the questions posed, by journalists, to the baboon.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Self-Involvement (SI) [imaginary interaction with the character from the text]	Managerial (MA) [task-management]	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
22	We agree. The house is where the people we like are.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC) 	Teacher 3	Whole Class ["we"]
23	You can make a lot of friends and learn a lot from each other. For us, this place is also our home.	Tolerance - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to acceptance of others]	Definition (DF) [part of a definitory conceptual work]	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 3	Whole Class ["for us"]

2.2.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This long interaction is divided into three episodes: the first one is constituted of threads 1 to 11, the second of threads 12 to 18, and the last one of threads 19 to 23. There is to be noted that the two first episodes share the same theme (e.g. the definition of "home"), but the type of contributions is very different between the two episodes (e.g. polyphony). During these first two episodes (especially the second one), the dialogue is mostly cumulative, with lots of isolated statements (were they justified), and a few collaborative acceptances and syntheses. In a lesser extent, the first episode is also argumentative, with some contributions produced to answer others (the length of threads is sometimes above 1 in this episode) and even some contrastive contributions (e.g. 4-2, 7-1). The third and last episode is mostly regulatory, with managerial contributions aimed at ensuring the smooth running of the lesson and the production of cultural artefacts.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The online interaction does not appear highly dialogic. However, the contributions in the first episode refer to groups of students, which means students have worked together to produce an unified opinion. Similarly, as contributions in the second episode are formulated with the voice of the whole class, we can hypothesise that they stem from oral discussion between students. Finally, the third episode also lets us hypothesise a rich oral dialogue between students to elaborate the artefacts. From a conceptual point of view, most of the dialogue is explicitly and deeply focused on the definition of the notion of "home" (first episode), or belonging (second episode) then tackling in two different ways the "Belonging" notion aimed by the lesson.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key concepts of the text?	As almost no contribution focuses on the wordless text itself (none except contribution 21, which is very vague regarding the text as it is about an artefact), the students almost did not use the notion of Empathy, which could have been used to interpret the baboon's actions.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	However, two contributions (e.g. contributions 18 and 23) implicitly use Tolerance, which is to be noted as it is not a main aim of the lesson. Both of these contributions being focused on a work on the definition of "home", we can expect that some students made a link between the notions of Belonging (through "home") and Tolerance.

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	The teachers take different roles during this online interaction: during the first episode, teachers are mostly mediators, taking the voice of groups of students and retranscribing their words on the platform, but sometimes take a guiding role, encouraging students in their reflexions or expressing reservations (e.g. contributions 4-1, 6-1, 7-1, 8-1). In the second thematic episode, the teacher apparently take fully the role of mediator (though there is probably oral, underlying guidance that we cannot grasp through online data), with all her contributions emitted with the voice of the whole class and the same structure (" <i>we belong to this place because...</i> "). The third episode is mainly one of task-managing for teachers, with the own teachers' voices expressed, but there is also a form of guidance in the last contribution.
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	During their mediation, the teachers mainly used the voice of groups of students (first episode) and of the whole class (second episode). There is however to be noted that some supporting contributions (thus with the voice of the teacher) were formulated as enunciated by the whole class (e.g 4-1, 6-1), maybe to make the support less explicit so that students do not feel "judged" by the teacher. Similarly, managerial contributions from the third episode were formulated as enunciated by the whole class (e.g. 19, 20). Teachers may have wanted to "soften" the task-managing for students, "hiding" it by presenting it as the continuation of the ongoing dialogue with the other class.

2.3. *The Hedgehog and the City* - Social responsibility / Social/civic competence - UCAM_AK_BG_B_7

18 contributions - 5 threads.

Minimal thread length 2, maximal 7 (detail 7 / 3 / 3 / 3 / 2)

All threads are initiated by the teachers.

2.3.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Social responsibility / Social/civic competence				
1	Good afternoon School X!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1	Good afternoon	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1-1	Have your class completed their vote yet!!!!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [task management]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1-2	We are busy persuading each other on what we would like to have in the park. Did you enjoy the start of the film? We did!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Managerial (MA) [task management] - Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]

1-1-2-1	hahahaha! Yes, we all loved it :) Our class has been very persuasive with what they think they would like to see!!!!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT) [this general comment is about students' behaviour and not properly about the task]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]
1-1-3	We propose that we should have 8 swings in the park because in other parks there are always queues for the swings	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
1-1-3-1	We like that idea, we had wondered about automatic swings for the very young, but in order to bring the community together, we propose a reading area in the park, where young and old can come together with their newspapers?	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to specific action to increase diversity, "bring the community together"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
2	We propose that we should have 8 swings in the park because in other parks there are always queues for swings	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
2-1	We feel that a community reading area would bring people of all ages together.	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to specific action to increase diversity]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
2-1-1	We like that idea however we feel that more people go to a library to read rather than a park. What would you do with the books when it rained?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) - Co-Construction (CC)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
3	We like your idea however we feel that most people go to a park to run around and not to read. What would you do with the books when it rained?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) - Co-Construction (CC)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
3-1	We would have a canopy to protect the books. However, thinking about it, you wouldn't run around on swings. However, if you are thinking about running around, we propose a maze?!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Co-Construction (CC) - Justification (JU) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) - Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]

3-1-1	We agree with your proposal of a maze. We propose having books as prizes for completing the maze then people could go and read them underneath the canopy.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
4	We love your proposal of a maze. Adding on to that idea we propose having books for prizes when completing the maze. These could then we read underneath the canopy.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
4-1	How lovely, extra swings is also a fantastic idea so that whilst people waiting to go into the maze, they could play on the swings???	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Inviting (IN) ["???"] 	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
4-1-1	Sounds like a great proposal to us. What about people who like heights? We propose a 4ft climbing wall to challenge people who like adrenalin based activities?	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to specific action to increase diversity]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ["to challenge..."] 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["us", "we"]
5	We love the idea of these proposals. What about people who like heights? We propose a 4ft climbing wall for those people who like an adrenalin based activity. Or maybe a zip wire instead?	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to specific action to increase diversity]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ["to challenge..."] 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
5-1	Sounds fantastic! We had thought about a mini-go ape idea, and a zip wire. We propose that the zip wire is a long one at the end of the climbing equipment, as a reward for making it to the top/end.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ["to challenge..."] 	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]

2.3.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	<p>This online interaction mediated by teachers is very highly dialogic. The interaction seems constituted of five different threads, but is in fact one thematic episode, "artificially" segmented into threads by a teacher who re-emits contributions in other threads, maybe for readability reasons on the platform. The 18 contributions (14, if we exclude the duplicates) are then in fact all part of the same dialogue. Furthermore, most of the contributions contains several advanced Dialogue Acts, which also indicates high dialogicity. This cumulative dialogue (few disagreement, lots of statements and acceptances) is then also very collaborative (lots of Co-Construction, Synthesis in the contributions) with more argumentative sub-episodes (e.g. contributions 2-1-1/3 , 3-1 and their constrative moves). However, the interaction does not seem to allow students to develop a rich conceptual work (see below).</p>
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	<p>Only a few contributions use (implicitly) the key notion of Inclusion, and this use is not sustained in the dialogue. All the discussion is centered on the activity of "elaborating a park", and the teachers do not guide students towards further work on the notion of Social/civic competences (the main objective of the lesson according to the lesson plan) or Tolerance/Empathy/Inclusion. Students then did not address at all the topic of social/civic competences (no contribution) and tackle barely TEI. Inclusion is yet being implicitly used in contributions, which could have been a lever to address the topic.</p>
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	<p>After a short regulatory sub-episode to start the interaction, where teachers briefly took the role of task-managers, they mostly contributed to the cultural literacy process as mediators. Teachers indeed mainly used the voice of the whole class, or spoke as enunciated by the whole class (e.g. contributions 1-1-2, 1-1-2-1). There is few or no trace of teachers' guidance in this dialogue. However, as noted above, students did not begin spontaneously the conceptual work on the objectives of the lesson, and teacher's guidance would have been required to help students attaining an higher-order thinking on the topic. Teachers appear "stuck" in their role of mediators, and they did not provide guidance even when some students' contributions using implicitly inclusion (e.g. 1-1-3-1/2-1) could have been a good lever.</p>
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

2.4. The Elephant and the Bicycle - Social responsibility / Social/civic competence - ID04_Lesson 6_UNIC_B

22 contributions - 5 threads.

Minimal thread length 1, maximal (detail : 5 / 4 / 11 / 1 / 1)

All threads are initiated by the teachers.

2.4.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Social responsibility / Social/civic competence				
1	GOODMORNING	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1	Goodmorning from the Grade B students of School AD	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-2	We are ready to begin, and you?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
1-2-1	So do we!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
1-2-1-1	The A2 class of School AA is ready to discuss the first question	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]

2	Who has the role of the elephant in our society? Who does the cleaning in the classroom, at school, in our home?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Self-Involvement (SI) [application of the text to real life]	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class [direct question + "our society"]
2-1	we all have the responsibility for cleanliness in the classroom, at school, in our home, in our village. But also the people who are responsible for cleaning, such as school cleaners and garbage collectors in our community.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
2-1-1	Do we have to have something in return in order to participate in the cleaning of our community?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class [direct question + "we"]
2-1-1-1	And we agree that everyone is responsible for the cleanliness of the area she/he is, whether this is the classroom, the yard, the school, our room, our house and our whole city. There are also people who work as cleaners of the space around us but this does not mean that we do not care about the environment around us. We do not need to wait something in return in order to participate in the cleanliness of our community or our school.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) [second sentence] - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) 	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we", "us"]
3	In the movie we watched, people were expecting the elephant to clean up all the rubbish and did not think that they too have a share of the responsibility.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to not helping others]	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
3-1	At the point 7:18!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-1-1	Our goal should be not to throw rubbish everywhere but in rubbish bins and recycling bins. In this way, no one will have to pick up the rubbish of others.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	Self-Involvement (SI) [application of the text to real life]	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]

3-2	Everyone is responsible for their garbage, if they had disposed the rubbish in the bins from the beginning, the elephant would not need to do so much work.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	Self-Involvement (SI) [application of the text to real life]	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-2-1	We should actively participate in the social welfare, without expecting anything in return.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
3-2-2	We agree with this and we should not expect anything in return because I collect my garbage or someone else's.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC) 	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
3-2-2-1	Can you name any jobs that help your community?	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [direct question + "you"]
3-2-2-1-1	the neighbourhood police officer, the mayor and the city council, the school's parents' association.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
3-2-2-2	We are all part of our community and we need to take care of it.	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to participation to a specific group]	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
3-2-2-2-1	We, in the first class thought that we could help our community: as employees in the garbage dump, in the recycling sector, paper, plastic, bus drivers so that people do not use their cars a lot and have a lot of exhaust fumes. We help the elderly people to cross the streets, postment, we paint on walls, we clean the gardens from weeds and pruning trees	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [contributes to define "social responsibility"]	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ["bus drivers so..."] 	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]

3-2-2-2-1-1	I am sorry for the spelling mistakes, I just saw it and I cannot fix it, here we are a bit tired. Thank you very much for the conversation, we will speak again soon.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 1	- Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["I"] - Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]
4	We write cleaning rules for our classroom and our school!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]
5	Thank you, we will speak again soon!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]

2.4.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This online interaction appears rather dialogic : despite that the dialogue is mostly cumulative, with students more reacting to teachers' questions than interacting together, one can see some co-constructive contributions (e.g. 2-1-1-1 and 3-2-2) and interactive regulatory sub-dialogues at the beginning and the end of the interaction (e.g. thread 1, contributions 3-2-2-2-1-1 to 5). Furthermore, the threads are pretty long, which indicates sustained discussion (especially in thread 3). From a conceptual standpoint (see below), the discussion in the central episode deeply explores the notion of Social Responsibility.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	

Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	Excepted the regulatory sub-episodes at the beginning and the end of the interaction, most of the dialogue is centered on conceptual work. More precisely, almost all contributions of students contribute to the definition of Social Responsibility. This work is heavily based on the text, as the first question from a teacher (contribution 2) already states a self-involvement and an application of the text into students' lives. However, there is almost no use of the notions of Tolerance, Empathy and Inclusion, as only two contributions (e.g. 3 and 3-2-2-2) implicitly use them. This suggests that even if students worked on social responsibility, they may have not linked this notion to the dispositions of TEI.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	This online interaction is complex regarding the teachers' role, as they take alternatively the three main roles of task-managers, guides and mediators. They are in the role of task-managers at the beginning and end of the lesson, with regulatory discourse aiming at ensuring the smooth running of the interaction (interpersonal relationship). They are more in a guide role when asking students questions with their own voice (e.g. contributions 2, 2-1-1, 3-2-2-1) aimed at fostering students reflexion on Social Responsibility (even if the questions sometimes appear too direct to effectively foster reflexion, almost containing the answer in themselves, e.g. contribution 2-1-1). These questions are variously direct, depending if the enunciator is the teacher (3-2-2-1) or the whole class (2, 2-1-1). Finally, they also are in the role of mediators in transcribing students' answers to their questions, taking the voice of the whole class or enunciating their own reflexions as the whole class'.
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

2.5. The Elephant and the Bicycle - Social responsibility / Social/civic competence - VU (lesson 6)

14 contributions - 7 threads.

All initiated by the teacher.

Minimal length of threads: 1. Maximal length of threads: 4.

2.5.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Social responsibility / Social/civic competence				
1	Let's talk.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
1-1	We should take care of our environment ourselves.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Whole Class ["we"]
1-2	We are already discussing. Here are our answers to the first question.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["we"]
1-2-1	We agree with that. That way we can take care of our nature. But not everyone, but then there would be no people to take care of other areas e.g. teachers, police officers.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]

2	Who takes on the role of an elephant? These are volunteers, but such jobs are done by people who have such a profession. Anyone can contribute. There are jobs that are done by certain people. Who wants that helps. Besides cleaners and street sweepers. It employs people who don't have the skills to do other jobs or people who don't have an education, or work that job just to make a living.	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [action to increase diversity]	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	Self-Involvement (SI) [identification to a character of the text]	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [Question from LP + following is not specified]
2-1	Who takes on the role of an elephant? Cleaners, handlers. But at the same time, we must take responsibility for managing our environment.	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	Self-Involvement (SI) [identification to a character of the text]	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	- Teacher Enunciator Teacher [Question from LP] - Whole Class ["we"]
3	Let's try to answer the second question.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified, task-managing]
4	Why do we have to take responsibility for actively caring for our community? If you don't take care of nature, there will be no fresh air, no trees, no flowers. Forests can catch fire if garbage is not managed. You won't want to be in the field if there is dirt.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole class [Question from LP + "we"]
4-1	We agree with your opinion :)	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
4-1-1	If there are no trees left, there will be no more of us all.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC)	Teacher 2	Whole Class ["we"]
5	Why should we take responsibility for taking active care of our community? Because not to complicate the work of others. After all, it is our responsibility and no one walks after us. We will help others more in the environment in which we work and will be. We must manage and prevent littering our environment. We believe that the more we work, the cleaner we all are.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole class [Question from LP + "we"]

5-1	Wisely said, children say and agree with your opinion.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [reference to "children" as exterior]
6	We should contribute to the well-being of society without expecting anything in return. We agree with this statement. If we take care of the environment ourselves, we will be happy. We think we will help ourselves, others and the environment. We think when we do a good job we do not have to ask for reward. We agree with this statement. But if you get paid, you can donate the money to charity. It will be doubly good work.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) 	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole class [Sentence from LP + "we"]
7	We should contribute to the well-being of society without expecting anything in return. We agree with that statement. If you give money to charity or sick children, it will be better for yourself, because you will know that a good job has been done. We believe that everyone has to do a good job in life and not one. Helping, being active, helping grandparents cross the street, or going to the store is also a good job. And if I give a candy for it, I thank it. We think that the reward for the work done sometimes motivates even more and more to do good work.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to helping others]	Definition (DF) [tentative definition of social responsibility]	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO) 	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole class [Sentence from LP + "we"]

2.5.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	The online interaction does not appear highly dialogic, as it is strictly structured by teachers' questions (related to the lesson and the role of the teacher, see below). The answers are only briefly discussed, mostly in a cumulative way (simple acceptances, e.g. contributions 4-1, 5-1), even if there is traces of cooperative dialogue (e.g. contribution 4-1-1). Nevertheless, many contributions contain different complex Dialogue Acts (e.g. justifications and syntheses), so we can hypothesise that students from a same class interacted orally to elaborate these contributions.

Form of the dialogue	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The online dialogue is rather lowly dialogic (see above). From a conceptual standpoint, most of the interaction aims at exploring the notion of social responsibility through a deep conceptual work (see below).
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The dialogue is structured by teachers' questions (both in its content and in the structure of threads), which aim at guiding students through a better conceptualisation and enactment of Social Responsibility (which is the main objective of the lesson). As such, the dialogue focuses on a conceptual work on this notion, with many contributions proposing a tentative definition of Social Responsibility, sometimes through involving students in the wordless text (e.g. contributions 2, 2-1). The dialogue then leaves few space for the discussions of the three key notions of Tolerance, Empathy and Inclusion, which are not explicitly linked to Social Responsibility. Nevertheless, Empathy (and in a lesser extend Inclusion) are implicitly used during the conceptual work on Social Responsibility, which can indicate that students start to form a link between theses notions.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	
Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	The teachers contribute to the cultural literacy process in various ways, as they seem very directive in this online dialogue. They are both task-managers and guide when asking the guiding questions from the lesson plan, which aim at guiding students through a better conceptualisation and enactment of Social Responsibility, and they are also in the mediator role, transcribing students' oral discussions on the platform (see below).
Role of the teacher	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	The teachers appear to be very directive in their role of mediators, with few contributions produced with the voice of the class, and furthermore only "simple" contributions, like acceptances (contribution 4) or minor co-construction (4-1). Several mediating contributions are instead produced with the voice of the teacher as enunciated by the whole class, and a mediating contribution is even produced as enunciated by the teacher (e.g. 5-1). This "locking" of the task by teachers can explain the rather low dialogicity of the interaction, as teacher may have been more focused on their students' achievement of the task (answering questions from the lesson plan) than on dialogue.

2.6. The Hedgehog and the City - Social responsibility / Social/civic competence - WWU (session 7)

13 contributions - 9 threads.

All initiated by the teacher.

Length of the threads 1 or 2.

2.6.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis			Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy Inclusion	Social responsibility / Social/civic competence				
1	oh la la	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher <i>[no specific mention]</i>
2	super	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Teacher <i>[no specific mention]</i>
3		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher <i>[no specific mention]</i>
4		<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Off-Task (OT)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher <i>[no specific mention]</i>

4-1	Suggestions for the school community - 5 trampolins // ropes course // school pets: horses, dogs, cat, etc. // school disco // the school's own swimming pool // bumper cars on the schoolyard // more soccer shooting targets // petting zoo // cafeteria cinema // PS4 (a gaming console) // games room Suggestions for the park: trampoline hall, bread vending machine for the ducks, kiosk with cheap prices, sleeping lawn with beds, inline skating park, water park, a lot of playground equipment, also a PS4, Switch (another gaming console), rollercoaster...	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Self-Involvement (SI) [suggestion of alternative action]	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
5	Unfortunately my video isn't loading correctly!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [DIALLS management]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["my"]
6	The animals won't be well in the city and they will be unhappy.	Implicit Use Empathy [feelings of a character from the text]	<i>Not coded</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
6-1	The hedgehog should become mayor.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Self-Involvement (SI) [suggestion of alternative action]	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
7	They will pool their money and buy food.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 3	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
7-1	They want to buy more space for themselves.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
8	quite clever, these animals – they are a good community, for sure	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
8-1	An animal community – they want a free „zone“	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]
9	Groupwork now in {names of the three towns of the schools}	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [task management]	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific mention]

2.6.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	After a first short episode (contributions 1-4) of regulatory dialogue where teachers' "chat" to test the platform and the communication, the dialogue is weakly dialogic and mostly cumulative, with disconnected statements (excepted managerial contributions 5 and 9). The structure of the threads does not seem to relate to the content of contributions, with for example contributions 4-1 (resp. 6-1) being a statement without link from contribution 4 (resp. 6). Students may have had very dialogic interactions in face-to-face discussions during this sequence with the guidance of their teacher, but this does not appear on the online data.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The interaction appear weakly dialogic. On the conceptual level, students seem almost exclusively focused on the wordless text, with only one contribution (contribution 6) implicitly using the concept of Empathy. Some other contributions (e.g. 4-1 and 7) refer very vaguely to TEI and thus cannot be considered as clear indicators for conceptual work.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The online dialogue appear very limited on the conceptual level, with only contribution 6 using -only implicitly- the concept of Empathy. Social and civic competences, which were the main objective of the <i>Hedgehog and the City</i> lesson, do not appear on the online dialogue. As the contributions appear very short and limited, we can expect that the face-to-face dialogue mediated by teachers in their classrooms was proportionally more developed and that the conceptual work still took place, but we do not have data to confirm this hypothesis.

<p>Task - Narration and ethical concepts</p>	<p>How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?</p>	<p>The apparent poor quality of the dialogue from conceptual and a dialogic points of view can be explained by the students' focus on the reconstruction of the text's narration. All contributions in the cumulative episode are indeed interpretations. Coherently with the low use of concepts, most of these interpretations are First-Level, with only one Concept-Oriented Interpretation (contribution 6). Contribution 4-1, which is the only contribution coded as Self-Involvement, is nevertheless rich, and we can suppose that the students discussed a lot with the guidance of the teacher to elaborate this long contribution.</p>
<p>Role of the teacher</p>	<p>How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction? To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?</p>	<p>The teachers mainly contribute to this discussion as mediators, and in a lesser extent as task managers. Mediation seems to be the main goal for teachers. The first short episode of regulatory dialogue is indeed focused on the smooth running of the discussion so they can properly mediate afterwards (as opposed, for example, to task management focused on the behaviour of children). The mediation however seem rudimentary, as teachers do not present the (mostly short) mediated utterances as coming from the class nor a specific child (Voice Teacher + Enunciator Teacher in all contributions). As noted above, it is plausible that teachers focused mainly on the face-to-face interaction with their own students, and not with each other, in order to contribute to the cultural literacy process orally.</p>

3. Secondary

3.1. *Emptiness - Empathy - HUJI (HUJI_C_JJos_9_G1)*

13 contributions - 7 threads - Minimum thread length: 1 - Maximal thread length: 4

All threads are initiated by students.

3.1.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis		Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts: Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
1	the two pictures we chose are: the picture where him and the woman are standing next to each other and are suddenly in color. This picture symbolizes how when two people are together they're no longer invisible, they're no longer lonely. They have each other	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) ["together"]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 2	Group
1-1	the second image is the one where the lonely man is walking in the snow, and that he's that transparent and missing that you don't notice him. It expresses the sadness and his lack of home for the rest of his life in loneliness	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("loneliness")]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	- Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC) [it's a different student from the same group]	Student 1	Group
1-1-1	the first picture is the one where the lonely man meets someone who feels just like him in her life, and then you see that they're both in their meeting no longer lonely and there's color and they're no longer transparent	Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) ["both in their meeting"]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	- Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 1	Group
1-2	the picture where the man stands in the white snow and you just don't see him, this image emphasize how much that person is lonely and invisible,	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("lonely")]	- Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 2	Him/herself [not specified]

2	In my opinion, the book is about how others aren't supposed to behave towards those who are lonely, and about how lonely people feel throughout their lives.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to action to implement to increase diversity] - Empathy - Implicit Use [reference to feelings] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	Statement (ST)	Student 1	Him/herself ["in my opinion"]
3	the book is about a transparent man who's not possible to sight by society surrounding him though he tries to contain and fill the people around him, the man feels lonely and empty and that's why he's transparent	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("lonely and empty")]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description (DS) ["transparent man"] - First-Level Interpretation (FLI) ["not possible to sight by society"] - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	Statement (ST)	Student 3	Him/herself [not specified]
4	the book tries to make us understand the complexity in loneliness and understand the effect of loneliness on the other	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("loneliness")]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	Statement (ST)	Student 3	Him/herself [not specified]
4-1	I think that in addition to what you said the book is also about: the book is about the effects of loneliness on people for example: willingness to help others break through a situation of loneliness (the caged bird) depressed, wants to be noticed etc	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("loneliness"), clear reference to helping others] - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to action to increase diversity ("break through a situation of loneliness")] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting/Discarding (AC/DC) ["in addition to what you said" implies implicit acceptance] - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) 	Student 2	Him/herself ["I"]
5	the book is about loneliness and emptiness as well, where the hero feels "turned off" until you can see that he already truly vanishes, unlike other colorful people of are not lonely. In my opinion, the book is a kind of a message according to which, there are lots of lonely people in the world, and together with people who feel "full" it gives you a sort of a choice, of what you prefer being, transparent or full of life the two parts I chose are the parts where he becomes really transparent and empty until he already disappears into the snow, which symbolizes the deep and heavy feeling of emptiness, and the part where he finds another transparent and lonely person, where in this part you can already see that something is missing in their heart, waiting for something to complete it	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [several reference to feelings ("loneliness, emptiness")]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Co-Construction (CC) ["as well"] - Statement (ST) 	Student 4	Him/herself ["in my opinion"]

5-1	I agree with [student]	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting/Discarding (AC/DC)	Student 5	Him/herself [not specified]
5-2	I agree with you and I would like to add, that this book also pertains to our life as there are people in the world who are very lonely and depressed, and we must assist them and be their friends and not hurt them anymore directly by not helping them.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("<i>lonely and depressed</i>"), clear reference to helping others] - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to action to increase diversity ("<i>assist them and be their friends</i>")] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accepting/Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) - Statement (ST) 	Student 1	Him/herself ["I"]
6	The book relates to our private lives since now especially in this generation everyone is connected and everyone can get to everyone through the existing available technologies today there are many situations where we feel lonely and lacking any person to talk to and that way too we know many people to whom we can help	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to feelings ("<i>lonely</i>"), clear reference to helping others] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ["<i>since</i>"] 	Student 3	Group [" <i>our</i> ", " <i>we</i> "]
7	the book wants to say that we as a society should be caring and empathetic to those who are alone and understand. what they are going through and stop their loneliness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Empathy - Explicit Mention (EM) ["<i>empathetic</i>"] - Inclusion - Implicit Use (IU) [reference to action to increase diversity ("<i>stop [the] loneliness [of those who are alone]</i>")] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	Statement (ST)	Student 1	Him/herself [not specified: " <i>we as a society</i> " do not refer to the group but is much larger]

3.1.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This online interaction between students (groupwork) is constituted of one single episode. The dialogue in this episode is both cumulative (lots of statements, length-1 threads) and collaborative (acceptances, co-constructions, answers to threads' initiating contributions). Even with the dialogue not being argumentative, the interaction thus appears rather dialogic. Furthermore, students appear very focused on the task, and there is no regulatory dialogue from students.
Form of the dialogue	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The dialogicity of the interaction between students is rather high (see above). From a conceptual standpoint, the interaction is very rich, as all contributions (except contribution 5-1, which is an isolated acceptance within the dialogue) use concepts (though implicitly) within a deep work of narrative reconstruction (see below).
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	Due to the instructions given to students (choosing two representative images from the wordless text), all of the dialogue is focused on the narrative reconstruction of the text. However, the students simultaneously do deep conceptual work on the key notion of Empathy (which is the main objective of the lesson) but also on Inclusion, combining it in several contributions (e.g. 2, 4-1, 5-2). As such, all interpretations produced by students are at least partly Concept-Oriented. Furthermore, if this conceptual work is only implicit for most of the interaction, the last contribution (e.g. 7) explicitly mentions the notion of empathy, which can indicate that students' reflexion on this notion attained an higher level even without the teacher's guidance (which is an achievement to be noted). This is to be correlated with the emergence of a deep and sustained self-involvement in the text from students during the dialogue, from contribution 4 to the end of the dialogue, which is another indicator that students have effectively built meaning from the text, as they clearly state that the book " <i>relates to [their] private lives</i> " (contribution 6).
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	This online interaction is exclusively between students, so we do not have indications on the role of the teacher here.
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

3.2. Baboon on the Moon - Empathy / Belonging - NOVA_C_EC_Baboon on the Moon_8

7 contributions - 7 threads. All initiated by students.

3.2.1. Coding Table

Label	Post content	Task analysis (Baboon on the Moon)			Dialogue Act Code	Polyphony	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Belonging ("home")				
1	Our group's opinion is that baboon's real home is the Earth because of his reaction looking at it, emotional and crying. It makes us think that he misses his home, the Earth.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ("because") 	Student 5	Group
2	Our group thinks that this is the image that best represents baboon's real home once this is the scene where we see the baboon crying, portraying sadness and missing his real home, due to the solitude felt on the moon.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	Explicitly Mentioned (EM) ["his real home"]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ("once") 	Student 2	Group
3	The scene that best represents baboon's home is the Earth because, although he lives on the moon, through the movie, we can conclude that he misses the Earth and he's sad on the moon. Home is where we feel comfortable and happy, that's why we believe that the Earth is the place that best represents his home.	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	Definition (DF) ["home is where..."]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ("because") 	Student 3	Group

4	<p>The moon represents solitude because he feels lonely and also sad.</p> <p>On the moon, the baboon dreams about going to Earth where he'll have other beings that will make him feel comfortable and safe through love and trust.</p> <p>The loneliness doesn't allow the baboon to feel happy on the moon and to consider it his real home, because home is a place where we feel safe and where we like to be.</p>	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	Definition (DF) ["home is a place where..."]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) - Self-Involvement (SI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ("because") 	Student 3	Group
5	<p>The music portrayed in this small video expresses the longing that the baboon feels towards its true home. The music is sad and melancholic but, at the same time, it reminds him of joyful and happy moments lived in his home. [Earth]</p>	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Description (DS) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) 	Student 5	Him/herself [no specific mention of a voice]
6	<p>What does the Earth represent?</p> <p>The Earth, in this movie, represents baboon's home. The baboon misses his home, where he felt good and safe. By playing his trumpet he shows his love to Earth.</p>	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) 	Student 1	Him/herself [no specific mention of a voice]
7	<p>The emotions portrayed by the music in this video are solitude, sadness and longingness, once it corresponded to baboon's expressions and it was slow, heavy and melancholic.</p>	Empathy - Implicit Use (IU)	<i>Not coded</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Statement (ST) - Justification (JU) ("once") 	Student 4	Him/herself [no specific mention of a voice]

3.2.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	In this sequence, students do not seem to discuss together on the platform. There may be some oral discussions within groups, but the online discussion does not appear dialogic, with a mostly cumulative discourse and no trace of co-construction.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	Despite the dialogue being mostly cumulative, the majority of contributions (all except contributions 5 and 6) contains a justification. Furthermore, from a conceptual point of view (see below), the dialogue appears moderately rich, since the work on TEI is only implicit.
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The dialogue does not tackle explicitly the key dispositions of TEI. Empathy (one of the main focus of the <i>Baboon on the Moon</i> wordless text) is used in all contributions, but only in an implicit way. During the online dialogue students refer to the baboon's feelings but never work explicitly of the concept of Empathy, as they seem more focused on the notion of Belonging, through explicit mentions and tentative definitions of "Home".
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	The students appear more focused on the task of narrative reconstruction than on the conceptual work on TEI and Belonging. Nevertheless, all of the produced interpretations are at least partly Concept-Oriented, which can indicate, along with the implicit use of Empathy in all contributions, that students are implicitly linking their interpretation of the text and the notion of Empathy.

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	This online interaction does not contain any contribution from the teacher, who probably made his/her guidance and task regulation orally during the sequence. We thus do not have sufficient information.
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

3.3. Baboon on the Moon - Empathy / Belonging - UCAM_AC_AL_C1_8

54 contributions - 20 threads.

Minimal thread length 1, maximal thread length 8 (detail : 1 / 4 / 1 / 2 / 2 / 3 / 1 / 4 / 3 / 1 / 1 / 5 / 2 / 5 / 4 / 8 / 3 / 1 / 2 / 1)

All initiated by students excepted thread 16, initiated by a teacher.

3.3.1. Coding Table

Note: Teacher's contributions are darkened to appear more clearly in the table

Label	Post content	Task analysis (Baboon on the Moon)			Dialogue Act Code	Polyphony	
		Use of Concepts		Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
		Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Belonging ("home")				
1	what do you think the message was?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 1 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
2	we think that home is somewhere where you feel safe?	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Group ["we"]
2-1	We also think this but we also think its somewhere you can be yourself and be happy	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 3 School 2	Group ["we"]
2-2	We do think that home is a safe place where we all feel comfortable and safe. Where we make memories and happiness	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) ["we do think"] - Statement (ST) - Co-Construction	Student 1 School 2	Group ["we"]
2-2-1	we think home is a place where you feel safe and welcome	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 1 School 1	Group ["we"]

3	how do you think belonging and empathy link towards the film?	Empathy - Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 6 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
4	What do you think the overall message was?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
4-1	The overall message was what does home mean to you	<i>Not coded</i>	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	Self-Involvement (SI)	Statement (ST)	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
5	We think home is somewhere where you can feel safe and can spend your time in. What do you think?	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Inviting (IN)	Student 3 School 1	Group ["we"]
5-1	We think home is where your family is and somewhere where you feel comfortable and safe.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Statement (ST) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 2 School 2	Group ["we"]
6	World	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
6-1	What do you mean by world? Elaborate please.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
6-1-1	Why do you think the world is shown here?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Description (DS)	Inviting (IN)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
7	what does the video suggest about feeling at home	<i>Not coded</i>	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 1 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
8	How does the video make you feel?	Empathy - Implicit Use [reference to peers' feelings]	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
8-1	The video makes us feel sorry for him and makes us want to give him comfort the fact how he has to wake up at 5AM to do so much work to light up the moon and no one sees what he is working for they just see the end result	Empathy - Implicit Use [reference to peers' feelings]	<i>Not coded</i>	- Self-Involvement (SI) - Description (DS)	- Statement (ST) - Justification (JU)	Student 1 School 2	Group ["we"]

8-1-1	we completely agree with what you are saying no one knows what he is doing so what is he doing it for?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 1 School 1	Group ["we"]
8-1-2	Has he chosen this? Even though he is away from home?	<i>Not coded</i>	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [not specified]
9	What were your ideas about the video?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
9-1	person one said she was very confused on why the baboon was crying and why it can play the trumpet. Person two says why is he on the moon. and I think he was sent there and he misses the earth.	Empathy - Implicit Use ["he misses the earth"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Description (DS) - First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Student 2 School 2	- Other Student ["person one", "person two"] - Him/herself ["I"]
9-2	our ideas about the video were, what was the meaning of this film ? what was the man doing?, does he control the planets?, why is he on the moon?,is the moon his? , where's his family ??	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Description (DS) ["why is he on the moon?"] - First-Level Interpretation (FLI) ["is the moon his?"] - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) ["where's his family?"]	- Statement (ST) - Inviting (IN)	Student 1 School 2	Group ["our"]
10	what do you think the overall message is?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
11	can team 2 your talk to our group 6 as we could not login	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [online platform management]	Student 6 School 1	Group ["we"]
12	We think that the baboon is trying to get attention from Earth by lighting up the moon.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Group ["we"]
12-1	we think that lighting up the moon is his job and that he is playing the trumpet.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Description (DS)	Statement (ST)	Student 6 School 1	Group ["we"]

12-1-1	Who do you think he works for or why is that his job?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- Inviting (IN) - Co-Construction (CC) [invitation to develop an idea, basing on this idea]	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
12-2	yeah we agree and perhaps that was why he was also playing the trumpet	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 4 School 1	Group ["we"]
12-3	We think that he is maybe working as the moon and that he feels lonely just like the moon as its the only planet next to the sun.	Empathy - Implicit Use ["he feels lonely"]	<i>Not coded</i>	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Group ["we"]
13	why do you think the baboon is on the moon?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Description (DS)	Inviting (IN)	Student 6 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
13-1	Maybe he was sent to the moon to keep it bright?	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	First-Level Interpretation (FLI)	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
14	What do you think home represents?	<i>Not coded</i>	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
14-1	a place where you belong feel safe and secureand have an emotional attachment towards a place .	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 6 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
14-2	we think home is a place you feel welcome and safe	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 1 School 1	Group ["we"]
14-3	home is where the people you love are	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
14-3-1	I agree...	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
15	We think that the Baboon feels lonely and far away from home and his family and friends.	Empathy - Implicit Use ["feels lonely"]	Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Group ["we"]

15-1	we think that the trumpet is a way of getting peoples attention as he is lonely	Empathy - Implicit Use ["is lonely"]	<i>Not coded</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Group ["we"]
15-1-1	We think that the Baboon plays the trumpet because he is bored and lonely.	Empathy - Implicit Use ["is bored and lonely"]	<i>Not coded</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Group ["we"]
15-2	we feel that he has a duty to be on the moon (it may be his job) but he feels alone	Empathy - Implicit Use ["feels alone"]	<i>Not coded</i>	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) ["job"] - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 6 School 1	Group ["we"]
16	As a class, some of the ideas that came out was the fact that 'home' isn't necessarily one place, it can be multiple places. What do you think?	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	- Inviting (IN) - Synthesis / Contrast (SY/CO)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["as a class"]
16-1	Home can be more than one place and it depends if you feel more comfortable or safe.	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
16-1-1	We feel like Home can be more than 1 place, its just a place where you feel safe and comforted with no worries	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Group ["we"]
16-2	We have many houses for example family our school and community club's	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST)	Student 1 School 2	Group ["we"]
16-2-1	I really like this idea!	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Teacher 2	Teacher Enunciator Teacher ["I"]
16-2-2	we agree that we have many houses that are part of our community	<i>Not coded</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC)	Student 1 School 1	Group ["we"]
16-3	we think that home place were you feel an emotional attachment to which can be multiple places.	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Definition (DF)	<i>Not coded</i>	Statement (ST) Co-Construction (CC) [build on "home is many places" to highlight "emotional attachment"]	Student 6 School 1	Group ["we"]

16-3-1	Ok we're leaving bye.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Managerial (MA) [online interaction regulation]	Student 2 School 2	Group ["we"]
17	do you think they are showing loneliness?	Empathy - Implicit Use [reference to peers' feelings?]	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Inviting (IN)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [not specified]
17-1	I think that the baboon was sent there and he misses the earth and he does feel lonely. What do you think?	Empathy - Implicit Use ["he feels lonely"]	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	- Statement (ST) - Inviting (IN)	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
17-2	Yes because he was crying by himself on the moon. No one there to comfort him	Empathy - Implicit Use	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC)	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]
18	we think that the baboon is trying to get earths attention as he needs someone to comfort him	Empathy - Implicit Use	<i>Not coded [too vague]</i>	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	Statement (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Group ["we"]
19	we think he is doing all these things for the earth yet by doing this he is not having fun what do you think?	Empathy - Implicit Use	<i>Not coded</i>	- First-Level Interpretation (FLI) - Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI)	- Statement (ST) - Inviting (IN)	Student 1 School 1	Group ["we"]
19-1	I think that's true. we think that he lights up the moon.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Description (DS)	- Accepting / Discarding (AC/DC) - Co-Construction (CC) [precision to previous contribution's "all these things"]	Student 2 School 2	- Him/herself ["I"] - Group ["we"]
20	how do you think he is staying alive on the moon? electric-ity? Food? Water? How do you think hes breathing and staying alive.	<i>Not coded</i>	<i>Not coded</i>	Description (DS)	- Inviting (IN) - Justification (JU) [the last sentence implicitly justifies the questions: repetition of "staying alive"]	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [not specified]

3.3.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	This online interaction between students appear dialogic: with many threads tackling different aspects of the text. Students took initiative to post contributions about the text, and peers dialogically contributed, as the threads can rassemble several contributions (see length of the threads). The whole interaction corresponds to one discussion between the many participants. This dialogue is mostly both cumulative and cooperative, with many statements, acceptances, but also invitations and co-constructions.
	What is the quality of their dialogue?	The dialogue appears rather dialogic (see above). From a conceptual standpoint, students work deeply on the notion of Belonging, through a conceptual work on the definition of "Home". However, this work is not always productive, and seems to fail to weave links between the notion of Belonging and TEI (see above).
Task - Narration and ethical concepts	Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?	The dialogue appears more focused on the concept of Belonging (through the notion of "home") than on Tolerance, Em- pathy and Inclusion. Empathy is mentioned explicitly very early in the discussion (contribution 3) but then only stays used implicitly by students during the discussion. As such, there is no tentative definition of empathy (Empathy - DF) during this discussion, which could have been expected from secondary students. Despite the apparent focus on Belonging, the links between this notion and TEI do not appear explicitly during the discussion. Furthermore, regarding the work on Belonging, one can see that some contributions appear redundant (e.g. contributions 5/5-1 and 14-1, on the characteristic "safe"), and that students sometimes missed the point of the text (e.g. contribution 9-1 where students are " <i>confused</i> "). As such, more guidance from the teacher could have be helpful for weaker students.
	How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?	

Role of the teacher	How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?	<p>In this discussion, the teacher is mainly in the role of guide : the three contributions 8-1-2, 16 and 16-2-1 were all aimed at helping students understanding the wordless text. However, the inviting contribution 8-1-2 meet no answer, and the accepting contribution 16-2-1 did not explicitly encourage students' to pursue their reasoning. Contribution 16 was the most effective guidance, as it stimulated students' reflexion, but it only produced isolated statements and failed at initiating a deep dicussion on the notion of "home". Maybe more guidance, or in another form (different questions or modalities of help) could have helped the students more effectively.</p>
	To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?	

3.4. Super Big - Tolerance - WWU

57 contributions - 19 threads - Minimum thread length: 1 - Maximal thread length: 23

Threads 1, 2, 4, 10 were initiated by the teacher.

3.4.1. Coding Table

Note: Teacher's contributions are darkened to appear more clearly in the table

Label	Post content	Task analysis		Dialogue Act Code	Speech	
		Use of Concepts: Tolerance, Empathy, Inclusion	Narrative Reconstruction		Locutor	Voice
1	How can I/can one foster tolerance? I personally. I / we at school? Society?	Tolerance-Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["I" means here a theoretical student more than the teacher him/herself]
1-1	You should accept everyone and show respect	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is respect, acceptance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-2	Put oneself in another's position.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) - [more relative to "empathy" rather than "tolerance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-3	You should show sympathy.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is fostered by communication"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-4	You should support others.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is an active attitude"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-4-1	And be helpful.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is an active attitude"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	• Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) ["and"]	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-5	If you notice that someone at school is alone/is being discriminated against, you approach them, talk to them and try to help them.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "Tolerance includes prevention of bullying"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

1-6	You should show empathy and offer help.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) - ["empathy" rather than "tolerance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-7	You can foster tolerance by mutually respecting one another regarding school and society.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is respect"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-7-1	We mean that you should spread acceptance in society.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is acceptance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Justification (JU) [the reformulation/precision gives reasons to accept the previous contribution] 	Student 3 School 1	Group ["we"]
1-8	If you see that someone is being bullied (e.g., in school), you shouldn't just look away/walk past but should help and support that person.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "Tolerance includes prevention of bullying"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-9	We are all just people, no matter what the colour of skin, what sexuality, what religion or what nationality.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to equality for people of different groups]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-9-1	How can I bring that message home to others?	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Whole Class ["I" means here a theoretical student more than the teacher him/herself]
1-10	It should be self-evident to be tolerant towards our fellow human beings	Tolerance-Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-11	Not only the external but especially the internal/personal qualities count	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to diversity of ideas and/or behaviours]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-11-1	You should be friendly, don't care about appearances.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "acceptances of our form of expression and ways of being human"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) [the contribution is a direct extending of the previous one] 	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-11-2	We mean that character is more important than appearances.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "acceptances of our form of expression and ways of being human"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Justification (JU) [the reformulation/precision gives reasons to accept the previous contribution] 	Student 2 School 1	Group ["we"]
1-12	You should always be honest.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) - [refers more to "honesty" rather than "tolerance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

1-12-1	You should be friendly, don't care about appearances.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "acceptances of our form of expression and ways of being human"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) ["and"] 	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-12-1-1	You should think and act liberally instead of conservatively.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is prompted by recognition of the universal human rights and fundamental freedoms of others'"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) [the contribution is a direct extending of the previous one] 	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-13	You can try to understand other people and maybe try to think through other perspectives on things. Also you shouldn't insist on your own opinion, but you should still have one.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) - [more relative to "empathy" rather than "tolerance"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
1-14	We can give unprejudiced thinking to the new generations. To our own children as well as to other children, for example as teachers or child care workers. We as students could try to educate people that are very intolerant.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is an active attitude", "tolerance is acceptance of diversity"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 2	Group ["we"]
1-15	Maybe protests should be done or we should talk more about it in school 🙋🙋	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is an active attitude", "tolerance is fostered by knowledge"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST) [even formulated as an hypothesis, the contribution is still a statement]	Student 3 School 2	Group ["we"]
2	Mother has to comfort	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI) [explains the motivations of a protagonist of the text ("has to") without relating to tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [no specific voice indicator]
2-1	I think the mother is also proud of her son because her son is helping people.	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI) [explains the motivations of a protagonist of the text without relating to tolerance]	Stating (ST) Justification (JU) ["because"]	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
3	The boy needs help.	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	Description (DS)	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

3-1	I think that the boy just needs some acceptance and I wouldn't necessarily define that as help. You should just try to deal with new and other things and not just turn your back or not get to near.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to acceptance of the diversity of people]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accepting/Discarding (AC/DC) [this contribution aims at discarding the one it answers] • Synthesis/Contrast (SY/CO) [the contributions contrasts with the previous one] • Justification (JU) ["<i>I wouldn't...</i>" gives reason to reject the first] • Co-Construction (CC) [this contribution stems from the previous one] • Statement (ST) ["<i>You should just try...</i>"] 	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
4	Why can't the character build trust?	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of others]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution questions the possible motivations of the characters with respect to the key concepts of the lesson]	Inviting (IN)	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [the question is asked directly to students]
4-1	The people are too prejudiced and don't want to be helped by the „giant“.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of the diversity of people]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 1 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
4-2	Maybe they're not open enough for new things. They are afraid of the boy although they don't know his intentions and run away at first before confronting something new.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of the diversity of people]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
5	Wants to help but everyone's afraid of him.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI) [" <i>wants to help</i> "] Description (DS) [" <i>everyone is afraid</i> "]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
6	People that run away are a symbol for everyone looking at the appearance of a person first before looking at personal qualities.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of the diversity of people]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [symbolism of the text regarding tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 1 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

7	This creature is so social that it gets help even though everyone was so mean to him.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	First-Level Interpretation (FLI) [the contribution explains the text referring to "tolerance" too vaguely]	Stating (ST)	Student 6 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
7-1	How can we define this? The people are understandably afraid, even if the >other< is displayed as extreme.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of others]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inviting (IN) • Co-Construction (CC) [the contribution stems directly from the previous one] 	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
8	He wants to help but isn't accepted because he is different.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of others]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
9	As you can see, the „condemned“ person isn't happy about it.	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of others]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 1 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
10	Give an example how you can promote tolerance in society today. (Especially after the events of Hanau) [explanation from the translator: In February 2020, a racist, right-wing extremist killed 9 people from migratory backgrounds and himself.]	Tolerance-Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inviting (IN) • Justification (JU) [the mention of Hanau gives more reasons to promote tolerance] 	Teacher 1	Teacher Enunciator Teacher [the question is asked directly to students]
10-1	Show more support, a human is a human, as has been mentioned, it doesn't matter what nationality or religion and you should act on that. You don't want to be killed abroad yourself either after all.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF "tolerance is prompted by recognition of the universal human rights and fundamental freedoms of others"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) ["as has been mentioned"] 	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
10-1-1	Give more attention to the topic and don't hush it up.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Co-Construction (CC) [the contribution is a direct extending of the previous one] 	Student 4 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
10-2	We have to bring more attention to this topic!	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF ""tolerance is fostered by knowledge"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Group ["we"]

10-2-1	People are too inattentive and don't realise what is really going on. Something has to happen before they realise something.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 2 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
10-3	You should explain cultures to people and give them an understanding of it and build bonds between cultures.	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF ""tolerance is fostered by knowledge"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
10-4	You can promote tolerance through promotion education strongly express a tolerant opinion yourself be a role model for others	Tolerance-Definition (DF) + [matching with CAF ""tolerance is fostered by knowledge", "tolerance is an active attitude"]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 3 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
11	Why is the cat larger than a human? 😞😞	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	Description (DS) [question about the events depicted in the text]	Off-Task (OT) [could be considered as an inviting move, but more probably a false "trolley" question ("👁️👁️")]	Student 6 School 1	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
11-1	Because it's not really, if you look closely, you can just make it out that it's an animated film but maybe if you maybe have some problems with your eyes it's understandable 😊😊	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT)	Student 1 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
12	I am a vegan	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT) [does not relate to the topic]	Student 4 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
12-1	Who cares? Does that help against tolerance in society?	Tolerance-Explicitly Mentioned (EM)	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [peer regulation]	Student 2 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
12-1-1	That doesn't belong to the topic.	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Managerial (MA) [peer regulation]	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
13	Seaweed	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT)	Student 4 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
14	Yeet	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT)	Student 5 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
14-1	👊👊	<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT)	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
15	The people are afraid of the boy because he is huge 🐱🐱🐱	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of the diversity of people]	Concept-Oriented Interpretation (COI) [the contribution explains the text using implicitly the concept of tolerance]	Stating (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

16		<i>Not coded</i> [not about tolerance]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Off-Task (OT)	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
17	We noticed that the cat isn't afraid of the boy and lets him help her. The goat at the end is though.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Description (DS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stating (ST) • Synthesis/Constrast (SY/CO) (contrast between the cat and the goat) 	Student 5 School 2	Group ["we"]
17-1	*The goat is afraid of him.	<i>Not coded</i> [too vague]	Description (DS)	Stating (ST)	Student 5 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]
18	I feel sorry for the boy because he is being ostracised just because of his size. :(Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to unacceptance of the diversity of people]	Self-Involvement (SI) [identification to one character of the text]	Stating (ST) Justification (JU) ["because"]	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself ["I"]
19	The character counts, not appearances or body height	Tolerance-Implicit Use (IU) [reference to acceptance of the diversity of people]	<i>Not coded</i> [not about the text]	Stating (ST)	Student 3 School 2	Him/herself [no specific voice indicator]

3.4.2. Interpretation table

Research questions		Elements of answer
Form of the dialogue	To what extent students effectively discuss together and answer to each other?	The two first thematic episodes of the whole dialogue puts students in a conceptual work about "tolerance" and about the text (see below "Task") There is little dialogicity in these first two phases, with a cumulative dialogue as most contributions are mere isolated statements with few traces of co-constructive dialogue (see contributions 1-4-1, 1-11-1, 1-12-1). As this lesson corresponds to a work between group of students, the discussions and dialogicity are probably oral within groups, but do not let trace on the online data. There is few traces of argumentative dialogue, excepted in specific contributions (<i>e.g.</i> 3-1).

	<p>What is the quality of their dialogue?</p>	<p>The overall dialogicity of this online interaction appears pretty low, with a cumulative dialogue without cooperation, and lots of disconnected statements. Despite some threads being very long (23 contributions in thread 1), there is rarely several successive contributions in a given thread, suggesting a low-dialogicity interaction. The "Question from teacher / Answers from groups of students" structure does not seem to promote dialogicity, and except for isolated argumentative or cooperative contributions (<i>e.g.</i> 3-1 and 7-1) the dialogue seems mainly cumulative and weakly dialogic. In the end of the lesson (since contribution 11) students begin to lose attention in a brief thematic episode of regulatory dialogue, where some students begin to "chat" and others try to regulate them. The conceptuality of the dialogue vary during thematic episodes, with some episodes with advanced conceptual work and others hardly conceptual (see below).</p>
<p>Task - Narration and ethical concepts</p>	<p>Which part of the dialogue is oriented towards the key european dispositions of tolerance, empathy and inclusion?</p>	<p>The task, for students, is divided in several different phases introduced by the teacher's questions. The first phase puts directly students in a deep conceptual work about "tolerance" and ways to foster it in different contexts. There is no focus on the text in this first phase (contributions 1 to 1-15), as students propose lots of tentative definitions of "tolerance", most of them matching with the CAF definition of the concept. A second phase of the students' task focus more specifically on the text, with the teacher introducing it at contribution 2 and further clarifying it at contribution 4. The students really involve themselves in the task since the contribution 4, with most of contributions 4-1 to 9 both focusing on the text and on the concept of tolerance. A third and last phase of the task begins with teacher's contribution 10, where students are asked again, using their new insights on the text, to give concrete examples of promotion of tolerance. This third phase seems more difficult to the students, with several off-task contributions (11 to 14-1, 16).</p>
	<p>How is this conceptual activity distributed between the different components of the task?</p>	
<p>Role of the teacher</p>	<p>How does the teacher contribute to the cultural literacy process during the online interaction?</p>	<p>The teacher produced few contributions in the online dialogue, most of them corresponding to guidance towards the conceptual work. Most of the guidance operated by the teacher is made through inviting moves, contribution 2 excepted. There is to be noted that the first teacher's questions (1 and 1-9-1) are formulated with the class as enunciator, maybe in order to push students to invest themselves, and the latter questions (4 and 10) are asked directly at students with the teacher as enunciator.</p> <p>It was to be expected that the teacher do not take the role of mediator, since students of this level can express themselves on the online platform. However, the reasons of the absence of clear task-management from the teacher are not very clear, especially with students producing several off-task contributions (11 to 14-1, 16).</p>

	<p>To what extent the teacher uses students' contributions during the interaction? In which specific aim?</p>	<p>The teacher here mostly gives instructions to students, without building on their answers. The only exception is contribution 1-9-1, where the teacher invites students to develop their reasoning. This contribution stays unanswered, which may explain that the teacher does not build again on students' contributions and focus on giving instructions to students.</p>
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